

MASTER OF MANAGEMENT
BM-5102 ORGANISATIONAL BEHAVIOUR

REFLECTIVE REPORT

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1. OVERVIEW

Taking a Master of Management (MM) in University Brunei Darussalam (UBD) after one year absent from the study was a lot of challenge for me. I will also need a new friend as my bachelor degree friend already took their Master after they finished their bachelor degree last year. After completing my bachelor degree in Sociology and Anthropology at Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences (FASS), I spent time on searching for a job in the private and government sector. For the last 8 months I spent time working with the private sector, I decided to continue studying for a Master of Management at UBD as I feel that my current job was a mismatch with my major in bachelor degree as well as I am thinking of getting a job in government sectors. Choosing a major in Master of Management was a result from my family opinions as management majors have a broad option in government sectors. Moreover, taking advice from my friends that are currently taking their Master of Management, motivates me to pursue the Master of Management in UBD.

One of the core modules in Master of Management is Organisational Behaviour. This module aims to provide theoretical and practical knowledge in organisational behaviour towards developing an understanding of the scope of organisational behaviour as a field of study and its potential value in today's organisational life. As I have no background in business major, I feel lost at the early month of learning. In addition to the COVID 19 situations, the education system was changing into an online platform using canvas UBD and Microsoft Teams. As this module was 100% coursework because of COVID 19, I feel demotivated as I do not know what to do and to whom should I ask when I am stuck doing the assignment given. Fortunately, the lecturer was able to respond quickly when I emailed the lecturer.

Learning this Organisational Behaviour module helps me in understanding individual differences and personalities in one organisation. As I am still working in the private sector, I somehow can relate the theory that is taught in this module. Other topics such as motivation, conflict and stress were delivered very well as I personally can relate to real situations in an organisation. I can highlight that this module helped me in the real world while I was doing the assignment both group and individual work. As both assignments related to the current situations, I can learn that every topic was important to learn deeper.

Towards the end of semester, I feel that every process of learning is kind of memories to me. As I learn in a new environment, new friends and new challenges I cannot think that I will survive this semester. Along the learning process I feel excited after spend 8 months working and I know that I need to keep learning in other to keep improving in my work environment.

2. THEORETICAL KNOWLEDGE

“Maslow believed that there are at least five sets of goals which can be referred to as basic needs and are physiological, safety, love, esteem, and self-actualization. Maslow (1943) stated that people, including employees at organizations, are motivated by the desire to achieve or maintain the various conditions upon which these basic satisfactions rest and by certain more intellectual desires” (as cited in Ramlall, 2004, p54). In this report, it can relate to doing better in assigned tasks or group work. In addition, to achieve a good and clear understanding of the topic learn in this module.

In addition, Kreitner (1998), *“McClelland’s in the publication The Achieving Society, published in 1961 described the theory of needs focusing on three needs: achievement, power, and affiliation. The need for achievement was defined as the drive to excel, to achieve in relation to a set of standards, to strive to succeed. The need for power was defined as the need to make others behave in a way that they would not have behaved otherwise. The need for affiliation was defined as the desire for friendly and close interpersonal relationships. Achievement theories propose that motivation and performance vary according to the strength of one’s need for achievement”* (as cited in Ramlall, 2004, p54-55). The three needs: achievement, power and affiliation can be seen when I am studying this master of management. The need for achievement to do well better than the degree major and to be able to be independent for future follow by power where this is in terms of group work where the need of one leader to lead the group and divide the parts fairly, so that, all of the group members are participating in finishing the group assignment. The need for affiliation is where people need friends to encourage them to do their best in the study or other factors.

“According to Robert House, he introduced the path-goal theory. He believes that a leader can use all of the following leadership styles and actually shift back and forth among them: Directive leadership - Where the leader expects the followers what to do and how, giving a schedule what to be done, maintaining the performance and clear role of a leader in the group. Supportive leadership - Support them in a friendly work environment, showing concerns of their wellbeing and treat them equally. Achievement-oriented leadership - Remind the followers of the organisation goals, expect them to be always in highest performance and keep improving in performance. Participative leadership - involving team members in decision making, consulting and asking what their suggestions are when making decisions” (Schermerhorn Jr, 2013, p362-363). This module introduces a different perspective of what a leader can be in an organisation. It is impossible to see if the individual did not experience the current COVID 19 situations. I believe that this theory explains the changes of a leader style during the crisis management. This theory might benefit me if I have the opportunities to be the manager in the company or get the job in government.

3. INDIVIDUAL OPINIONS AND CONTRIBUTIONS ON THE GROUP ASSIGNMENT

My contribution in the group assignment was searching some of the literature review, creating some survey questions and google forms in virtual meetings with my group team members. When creating a google forms we struggle a bit because the last time we used the google forms is when we take LE module during the first year of bachelor degrees. In addition, compiling findings of the survey question were also part of my contribution together with my group members. I am also more focus to contribute the survey to local student as I have no connection with the international students. In addition, as this group assignment are more into survey findings it is a lot easier to do the report as I can view the finding through my phone and discuss with the group members in compiling the findings. They have their own contribution to the group assignment. Furthermore, my group members and I were able to have great chemistry and know what task to do in group assignment.

4. OPINIONS OF THE TEAM MEMBERS ON THE GROUP ASSIGNMENT

From my group members' opinion about my contribution in the group assignment Syhadah said that I am contributing in compiling some findings and literature review as well as giving a positive vibe which motivates her to do the assignment and be able to bring the other members together to do assignments before the due date. My second group member is Liyana, she said that I am an easy-going person that are easier to discuss about the group assignment and am willing to do any part. The last group member is Muqri, He mentioned that I performed well in finishing all the assigned tasks given and always committed in sharing ideas on what we should include in our findings. Afterall, I am lucky to know them during my time study of master degrees. When you have that chemistry, the group work is easier and can compromise with each other. There are no issues in who doing the part and who does what. You automatically know what to add and can discuss it anywhere and anytime.

5. OUTCOMES OF THE GROUP ASSIGNMENT

Doing a group assignment at master level was different during the degree level. I could say that a master degree teaches us to be more committed in the assignment given and more mature to know that it is a group work to be more successful and get a better grade. The outcome from the group assignment was that my group member and I were able to finish it earlier than the due date. This is because everyone from the group member was satisfied with the findings and being able to work together such as sharing the ideas as well as have no issues on the ethics forms. The case study topic was about Modeling ethical attitudes and behaviours under conditions of COVID-19 with online learning: The case of universities in Brunei. This study should explore the impact of COVID-19 on relationships between personal and organizational characteristics, personal values, ethical perceptions and behavioural intentions using the online

learning platform. A causal model should be used to test using data obtained from a national sample of universities in Brunei. This was selected by Syahadah as she is kind of a quick learner from all of the team members.

I was satisfied with the outcome as one of my group members gave an interesting idea as to compare it with the international students. Liyana also did a great job in finalise the report. The outcomes of group assignment were to know what are the student's perceptions of online learning and identify their behaviour towards this change education systems. Basically, I feel grateful to have them as my group members as they have different personalities and for some reason be able to give me motivation to finish my master. As each of them have different personalities, they can back up my weakness. Overall, to have a better group work is everyone contributing together in a group assignment.

6. INDIVIDUAL STRENGTH AND WEAKNESS

As this is almost the end of the semester, I learn a lot from both individual and group work assignments. For the individual assignment, the strength would be I have no pressure in completing my task as this is an individual task. I have a lot of time to plan, draft and organise my thoughts when doing the individuals. The weakness would be procrastinating because no one would ask me to finish my work. In addition, the individual assignment is different with my friends, so if I stuck with my assignment, I cannot ask them what should I do because I am doing different topics but it is helpful in structuring the report. My weakness is also that I am a slow learner so I spend more time to understand the topic and have no background in business major, make it disadvantages to me. For the group assignment, my strength might be I am good at finishing my task as I feel that I need to finish it quickly to prevent I do not interrupt in finishing the reports. Sometimes, in group work there is a part that needs to be done first before others group members can do it. As for the weakness, it the same as in individual because I am a bit slow learner in finding the literature review and compiling the findings. My group members help encouraging me just to do it slowly but great outcomes.

For this semester, I need to learn to be quick in every task as it will help me in the world of searching for a job. This is because every year, thousands of people are graduating and compete to get a job. Equally, according to Musa & Idris (2020) point out that *"From the employers' perspective, the youth seeking employment lack the wisdom, self-awareness and the passion towards improving their leadership capacity. Self-awareness entails an understanding of one's strengths, weaknesses, and limitations, of how they gather and process information, of how they handle ambiguous and stressful situations, and of how they are perceived by and interact with others"* (p94).

7. RECOMMENDATION AND CHANGES

Being able to finish my master of management is my main goal for now. In situations of the COVID 19 pandemic that restrict the learning system, it also helps my study as I have a lot of time to focus on what is important and organise my work as well as motivate myself to do better in the future. As COVID 19 is still ongoing, I predict that the next semester will still use the online learning platform but it will be better than this semester as I already experience and adapt to this change. The recommendation could be in term of improving communication skills, learning to use the online learning platforms for easier access. The key important during this COVID 19 learning situation is to be able to communicate with group members. Some other modules challenges are the difficulties in finishing the group work assignment because of miscommunication as well as the difficulty in meeting the group members physically.

8. SIGNIFICANT OF REFLECTIVE REPORTS

This reflective research is important because it helps individuals learn from a particular practical experience. It will also help individuals to make connections between what you are taught in theory and what you need to do in practice (“Genres in academic writing: Reflective writing”). What makes Organisational Behaviour relate to the real world is because both individual and group work are an observation or explanatory research of how the company was operating with different topics and current or past issues. Through this module, I know how to relate the theory that is taught with the current situations and I can see that different organisations have different circumferences. At the end of the semester I would like to keep in touch with my friends to keep pursuing the master of management and together changing into a better manager that are thought in the master of management not only in remembering the theory but also be able in practicing the actions as a manager.

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